

The role of spatial resolution and vertical accuracy of global DEMs in delineating stream networks

Petr Basta

Faculty of Environmental Sciences
Czech University of Life Sciences
Prague - Suchbát, 16500, Czechia
bastap@fzp.czu.cz

Jana Maresova

Faculty of Environmental Sciences
Czech University of Life Sciences
Prague - Suchbát, 16500, Czechia
maresovajana@fzp.czu.cz

Vitezslav Moudry

Faculty of Environmental Sciences
Czech University of Life Sciences
Prague - Suchbát, 16500, Czechia
moudry@fzp.czu.cz

Abstract—The efficacy of global digital elevation models (DEMs) derived from satellite observations is of paramount importance for hydrological applications, including stream network delineation. However, their effectiveness is constrained by spatial resolution and vertical biases introduced by vegetation and man-made structures. This study evaluates the performance of various global DEMs, including bare-earth models, in a Central European mountainous region. Utilizing lidar-derived digital terrain models (DTMs) and national stream networks as reference data, this study shows that bare-earth DEMs have higher vertical accuracy than conventional global DEMs across all land cover types. However, it is concluded that vertical accuracy alone is not a reliable indicator of a DEM's capacity to delineate stream networks. Instead, terrain slope and land cover exert a more significant influence on the accuracy of the delineated stream network. While the use of higher-resolution DEMs (e.g., 12 m TanDEM-X) has been shown to improve stream delineation, it has also been demonstrated to amplify errors related to vegetation bias. The study emphasizes that DEM selection should be based on their performance in delineating stream networks, rather than solely on vertical accuracy. The findings underscore the necessity of enhanced vegetation and building offset removal in high-resolution DEMs to optimize their applications in hydrology.

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) are essential for hydrological applications, such as flood modelling [1] and stream network delineation [2]. However, their accuracy is often compromised by vertical biases and resolution limitations. DEMs derived from satellite radar or optical sensors frequently overestimate terrain heights due to their inability to penetrate dense vegetation or detect terrain beneath man-made structures [3, 4]. As a result, the effectiveness of DEMs for hydrological modelling depends not only on their vertical accuracy but also on

their ability to reflect hydrologically relevant terrain features [5, 6, 7].

Our study evaluates eight global DEMs, including both original and bare-earth models, to assess their accuracy in stream network delineation. The study focuses on the area of Giant Mountains in Czech Republic (Fig. 1), a region with diverse topography and vegetation cover. Using lidar-derived Digital Terrain Models (DTMs) and national stream networks as reference datasets, we analyzed how land cover, terrain slope, and DEM resolution influence the accuracy of stream network delineation.

Figure 1. The reference stream network acquired from the Digital Database of Water Management Data (www.dibavod.cz; Czechia) and Polish National Geoportal (geoportal.gov.pl; Poland) in comparison to global river networks data sets.

The study aims to address three key questions: (1) how does DEM vertical accuracy vary across different land cover types; (2) how do slope and land cover influence the accuracy of stream network delineation; (3) whether higher resolution (e.g., 12m TanDEM-X) or vegetation bias removal (e.g., FABDEM) is more important for improving stream network delineation. By answering these questions, the study seeks to determine which DEM provides the most reliable representation of stream networks for hydrological modelling.

II. METHODS

The study evaluates eight DEMs categorised into two groups: (1) Original DEMs (digital surface models): SRTM (90m spatial resolution), TanDEM-X (12m and 90m), NASADEM (30m), and Copernicus DEM (COP; 30m), and (2) Bare-Earth DEMs: FABDEM (30m) [8], MERIT (90m) [9], and Continental Europe DEM (CON, 30m) [10], which have undergone processing to remove either vegetation offset (MERIT), or both vegetation and building offsets (FABDEM and CON, respectively). As a reference, we used a high resolution lidar-derived DTM (ALS) that was acquired in 2012 during the leaf-on period using a small-footprint airborne lidar system (RIEGL LMS Q - 680i). The ALS point cloud density was at least 4 points per m²; we used the ground points to generate a digital terrain model (DTM) at a 2 m resolution. Accuracy assessment involved the following steps:

First of all, the vertical accuracy evaluation was assessed. Each DEM was compared against the reference ALS to determine errors in elevation representation. We calculated several validation metrics, but for simplicity, we only show the root mean square error (RMSE). Subsequently, we delineated stream networks and evaluated their accuracy using national hydrological dataset as a reference. Accuracy was measured based on intersection points, proximity to reference streams using eight buffer zones ranging from 0 and 200 m, and average distance. Finally, the accuracy of DEMs and delineated stream networks was evaluated with respect to terrain slope and land cover (forest, non-forest, and urban).

III. RESULTS

Bare-earth DEMs performed better than original DEMs across all land cover types (Fig. 2) and slopes (Fig. 3). Non-forest areas showed the best DEM accuracy, followed by urban areas, with forests having the highest errors (Fig. 2). The RMSE increased with the slope in non-forest areas across all models. In forests, this relationship was less apparent, especially for very high slopes (Fig. 3).

DEM with coarser resolution yielded a lower number of intersection points with reference streams (Table I), indicating more accurate stream network delineation. In addition, the higher was a particular DEM's spatial resolution, the greater was the proportion of vertices falling within the narrower buffer distance categories (Fig. 4). Stream networks extracted from bare-earth

DEM were more slightly accurate than those derived from original DEMs (Fig. 4).

Figure 2. Distributions of height differences (compared to the lidar-derived DTM) for all evaluated DEMs for urban, non-forest, and forest areas. The vertical dashed line represents zero (perfect fit).

TABLE I. THE NUMBER OF INTERSECT POINTS

DEM	Number of points that intersect reference streams
SRTM	3,554
NASADEM	5,151
TanDEM-X (90m)	3,408
TanDEM-X (12m)	8,161
COP	5,484
MERIT	3,869
CON	5,167
FABDEM	5,447

Figure 3. Effect of the slope on the accuracy (RMSE) of global DEMs.

Figure 4. Percentages of vertices of DEM-derived streams falling within seven buffer zones from the reference stream network.

However, the accuracy of derived stream networks varied considerably across land cover and slope categories (Figure 5). In fact, land cover and slope affected the accuracy of the delineated stream networks more than the resolution and vertical bias of the adopted DEM. The slope had an inverse effect on DEM accuracy and stream delineation: (1) in DEM elevation accuracy, errors increased with steeper slopes, especially in non-forest areas; (2) in stream network delineation, accuracy improved with increasing slope, likely because steeper slopes facilitate more distinct drainage patterns. Furthermore, streams in forested areas were delineated with higher accuracy than in non-forest or urban areas, despite forests being the most challenging land cover for DEM vertical accuracy.

Figure 5. Average distance (in meters) of the evaluated DEM - derived streams from the reference stream network in three slope and land cover categories, respectively. Urban (U), non - forest (NF), and forest areas (F).

IV. CONCLUSION

Overall comparison of all assessed DEMs is shown in Table II. The study demonstrates that vertical accuracy alone is insufficient for evaluating DEMs for hydrological applications. This underscores the need to include stream network delineation in the quality assessment of global DEMs. While higher resolution improves spatial detail, removing vegetation and building-induced biases is equally important for accurate stream extraction. Among the evaluated DEMs, FABDEM performed the best overall, making it the most suitable choice for hydrological studies. As DEM technology continues to evolve, future models should focus on balancing high resolution with effective bias removal to optimize performance in diverse landscapes.

TABLE II. COMPARATIVE PERFORMANCE OF DEMs

DEM	Comparative Performance		
	<i>Vegetation Bias Removed</i>	<i>Vertical Accuracy</i>	<i>Stream Network Accuracy</i>
SRTM	No	Moderate	Low
NASADEM	No	Moderate	Low
TanDEM-X (90m)	No	Low	Moderate
TanDEM-X (12m)	No	Low	High
COP	No	Low	Moderate
MERIT	Yes	High	Moderate
CON	Yes	High	High
FABDEM	Yes	Highest	Highest

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